

A Field Visit Report on Birgunj Prison

Parsa district , Nepal

Submitted to

Department of B.A.LL.B program

Madhesh University, Birgunj

**For the fulfilment of Practical training Paper II of B.A.LL.B 3rd Semester
Under Clinical Course (CI . 300/03)**

Submitted by

Dayanidhi Tiwari

<https://orcid.org/0009-0000-2786-3701>

B.A.LL.B ,3rd Semester,

Roll. No:74

Regd.No. MU-01-00029-2024

ABSTRACT

The prison system as core institution of criminal justice, is designed not only for confinement but also for rehabilitation and reintegration of offenders into society. Yet, in Nepal, prisons continue to grapple with structural deficiencies and human rights concerns. This Field based report is grounded in the broader context of prison systems, exploring their universal evolution as well as Nepalese prison development, critically examines the condition of Birgunj Prison (Parsa District Prison, Nepal) within its historical , legal context, evaluating its organizational structure, evaluate the physical living conditions within the prison (Health facilities, overcrowding, etc.). & compare them with the standards outlined in the Prison Act and relevant national laws.

During the visit, many problems were found, such as overcrowding, poor healthcare, lack of legal help, and limited rehabilitation programs. Issues related to infrastructure, mental health care, and management were also noticed. However, the study had some limits like short visit time, limited access, and less available data. So, In order to investigate these issues, the study employs qualitative methods, including field visits, direct observation, and interviews, supplemented by secondary data from reports, newspapers, and legal frameworks. The methodology also integrates legal framework analysis to compare existing conditions with the provisions guaranteed under Nepali law.

Even with these challenges, the report gives useful information about the realconditions inside Birgunj Prison. It also points out the urgent need for changes such as upgrading infrastructure, expanding healthcare and education, improving internal and security management, and ensuring adequate budget allocation. Such reforms are necessary to uphold human rights and move toward a more just ,effective correctional system as well as hopes to help in making better policies to protect prisoners' rights in Nepal.

Keywords: Birgunj Prison, Overcrowding, Prison Reform, Prison Act, Healthcare, Rehabilitation, etc.

DECLARATION

Dayanidhi Tiwari, hereby declare that the field visit project work titled " **Birgunj prison** " submitted to Madhesh University, is an original work conducted by me as part of my BALLB 3rd semester. This project has been completed under the guidance **Mr Swarn Pokharel** and **Mr Rupak Mandal** of Birgunj prison head and had an extensive discussion and interview on various topic related set of question.

All the data mentioned in the report are either accumulated by us as a result of our field visit or taken from credible sources which are ethically guided as per the guideline provided so far. This shall be able to make us liable to bear any of the consequences if found guilty of any misdeeds.

.....
Dayanidhi Tiwari
BALLB 3rd Sem ,2nd Year
Madhesh University
Birgunj Parsa , Nepal
Date:-2082-05-11

AKNOWLEDGEMENT

This field based Report entitle on "**Birgunj prison** " has been prepared as required by the central department of law for partial fulfillment of 3rd semester , Bachelor of Arts and Bachelor of law (BALLB) under MU.

First of all I would like to thanks Madhesh University for providing this kind of opportunities and helpful to improve the efficiency of students to complete job. This Project work provide a chance to the students to develop their mind and skill by doing research work. I have experienced with new challenges opportunities and people and I think this could be supportive in my future. This research work make me know about we can make presentation and analyze a report. I have chosen to research about solvency and profitability.

Many helpful hands are involved to support me for preparing this report. My sincere thanks to go all the member including **Mr Swarn Pokharel & Mr Rupak Mandal** of Birgunj prison for providing the require data and statics related to this report.

I would like to express my deep gratitude towards reverent Associate Subject teacher **Adv Narendra sir** & coordinator of Madhesh University **Mr Bal krishna Dahal** for inclusive and constant guidance, who have immensely contributed their time and labor to guide me for the preparation of this report. Without their guidance and valuable suggestion, it would have been extremely difficult to make this work fruitful.

Dayanidhi Tiwari

Roll No:- 074

Abbreviations

B.A. LL.B.	:	Bachelor of Arts and Bachelor of Laws
UN	:	United Nation
UDHR	:	Universal Declaration of Human Right
ICCPR	:	International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights
DAO	:	District Administration Office
DoPM	:	Department of Prison Management
Art.	:	Article
Sec	:	Section
SEE	:	Secondary Education Examination
NEB	:	National Education Board

GLOSSARY OF TERMS

Term	Definition
Prison	; A state-controlled institution where individuals are confined as punishment after being convicted by the court of law.
Detainee	; A person held in custody who has not yet been convicted of a crime but is awaiting trial or legal proceedings.
Inmate	; An individual who is serving a sentence in a jail or prison following a court's judgment.
Rehabilitation	;The process of restoring a convicted person to a useful life through Education counseling, and vocational training within the correctional system.

|

Parole ; The conditional release of a prisoner before the completion of their sentence, based on good behavior and legal provisions.

Open Prison ; A low-security prison where prisoners who meet specific criteria can work or study outside during the day and return in the evening.

Community Service ; Unpaid work assigned by the court as punishment, where offenders contribute to the community instead of serving jail time.

Fine ; A monetary penalty imposed on an offender by the court as a form of punishment, often for minor or non-violent crimes.

Overcrowding ; A situation where the number of inmates exceeds a prison's capacity, causing strain on infrastructure, health, and living standards.

Naika ; A prisoner chosen by jail authorities and fellow inmates to manage internal discipline and coordination in prison blocks.

Jailer ;- The head administrative officer of a prison, responsible for overall operations, discipline, and inmate management.

Prison Act, 2079 ; The principal law governing the operation of prisons in Nepal, detailing inmate rights, administration, and jail management procedures.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Title	Page no.
ABSTRACT	2
DECLARATION	3
AKNOWLEDGEMENT	4
Abbreviations	5
GLOSSARY OF TERMS	5
CHAPTER : 1	9
INTRODUCTION ,	9
1. 1 Background	9
1.1.1 Historical Development of Prison system	10
1.1.1.1 Universally Development.....	10
1.1.2 Meaning of prison	16
1.1.3 Terminology used by different countries.....	17
1.1.4 Introduction to Birgunj Prison (Parsa District Prison)	18
1.2 Statement of Problem	19
1.3.Objective of the Birgunj Prison visit	19
1.4 .Significance of the study	20
1.5.Scope of the Study.....	20
1.6 Limitation of study	21
CHAPTER:- 2	21
LITERATURE REVIEW	21
2.1.By Republica Post	21
2.2 BY Kathmandu Post.....	21
2.3 Inmates in Birgunj prison subjected to torture, extortion.....	22
CHAPTER:- 3	22
Methodology	22
3.1 Date collection method.....	23
3.2 Data Interpretation & Analysis.....	23
3.3 Legal Framework Analysis.....	24
CHAPTER:4.....	24
DATA ANALYSIS & DISCUSSION	24

4.1 Visitor Screening and Entry Procedures at Birgunj Jai	24
4.2 Organizational set up of Prison	25
4.3 Compare Present condition of birgunj prison to past one with their legal provision	26
4.3.1 Prisoners Capacity & no of prisoners {Overcrowding}	26
4.3.2 Health Facilities.....	27
4.3.3 Education.....	29
4.3.4 Direct and Daily Expenses	32
4.3.5 Employment facilities inside Prison.....	33
4.3.6 Activities Performed by different department in Birgunj Prison.....	34
CHAPTER: 5.....	34
FINDINGS	34
CHAPTER:6.....	37
CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATIONS.....	37
6.1 Physical Structure.....	37
6.2 Direct and Daily Expenses	38
6.3 Internal Management.....	38
6.4 Healthcare.....	38
6.5 Security Management.....	39
REFERENCES;.....	39
APPENDICES.....	40

CHAPTER : 1

INTRODUCTION ,

1. 1 Background

Democracy and the rule of law are complementary to each other. In order to establish the rule of law, it is considered inevitable to run the government according to the laws created by the people's representative institution Parliament and to end impunity. By punishing the criminals who violate the law, impunity will end and help in building a moral, clean and civilized society and the legitimacy of the government will also be established, but the punishment given to the criminals should be humane. In the United Nations Universal Declaration of Human Rights 1948, no one shall be subjected to physical torture, grossly inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment, and no one shall be subjected to arbitrary arrest, detention or deportation. Nepal is a party to various human rights treaties. By assimilating this, human rights, democracy, rule of law have been included in the preamble of Nepal's constitution itself.

The Constitution has expressed its commitment to the concept of civil liberties, fundamental rights and the rule of law, and has guaranteed the citizens the right to freedom, the right to justice and the right against torture. The constitution of Nepal has ensured that no person shall be deprived of personal liberty except according to the law, no person shall be detained without being informed of the reason for his arrest, the arrested person shall have the right to seek advice from a legal practitioner of his choice from the moment of arrest, the right to be heard by a legal practitioner and the consultation and advice given by such a person with his legal practitioner shall be confidential, no physical or mental torture shall be given to an arrested or detained person and he shall not be treated cruelly, inhumanly or humiliatingly.

In 1990, the basic principles of the treatment of prisoners declared by the United Nations General Assembly stipulate that every prisoner and prisoner shall be treated with respect in accordance with human value and dignity, and shall not be discriminated against on the basis of sex, race, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, wealth,

birth or any other status. Similarly, the rights of justice and others are ensured as fundamental rights in the Constitution, while the Civil Code 2074, Police Act, 2012, Children Act, 2075, Torture Compensation Act, 2053, Senior Citizens Act, 2063 etc. have provisions regarding minimum humane treatment to be given to prisoners. Even directive orders issued by the Supreme Court at various times have emphasized the need to ensure humane treatment of prisoners and to protect human rights.

It is the responsibility of the state to protect the human rights and guarantee the safety of the people in prison. People in prison need to be treated accordingly in order to reform them and make them worthy and capable citizens. It is also the responsibility of the state to facilitate their social rehabilitation after serving their imprisonment by providing them with education and skills and training them in productive work. Ensuring the respect, protection and promotion of human rights and individual freedom through fair hearing becomes the duty of the state. Therefore We students of BALLB on 13.12.2081 constituted a educational visit for the fulfillment of Clinical Practical to conduct on-site monitoring and submit a Research report for the fulfillment of Clinical Practical regarding whether the person in prison is being treated humanely, whether they are not allowed to visit relatives or law enforcement officers whenever they want, whether the minimum basic facilities are available or not.

1.1.1 Historical Development of Prison system

1.1.1.1 Universally Development

The idea of prisons goes back to ancient times, with the earliest records found in Mesopotamian and Egyptian civilizations around 1000 BC. In those days, prisons were often underground rooms where people stayed until they were either sentenced to death or made into slaves.

Ideologically , The prison system is not very old. It started being used as a form of punishment only in the late 1700s, mainly to replace the death penalty. Before that, people

were kept in custody only while waiting for their trial. These detention places were usually near the courts. The conditions were very bad—dark, dirty, crowded, and sometimes prisoners were tied up like animals. After the court made a decision, people were usually given death punishment, beaten, or made to pay a fine.

Over time, especially in the 18th century, societies started changing their views. Instead of punishing people physically, they began using prisons as a way to correct behavior. This change was driven by more humane thinking—people began to see criminals as human beings who could change for the better. Thinkers like **Voltaire and Cesare Beccaria** were key in spreading these ideas, pushing for fairness and justice in how society treats those who commit crimes.

Later, when people started caring more about human rights and fairness, these harsh punishments became less popular. Slowly, the prison system developed as a new way to punish people. But this change took time.

While the ancient concept of prison was all about threat, torture, violence, bloodshed, the proper idea of prison incorporated three major areas: punishment, deterrence, and rehabilitation. It is no longer only meant to be an extreme kind of corporal punishment. The former prison **Shepton Mallet Prison** in the **United Kingdom** is regarded as oldest prison but closed in 2013 while the 1798 Penitentiary House is the oldest prison in operation located in New York City, the United States.

In 1757, Britain started the **Bridewell** Prison to keep beggars and homeless people. They were forced to work, and some were sent to other places to work. In 1773, Belgium opened the Ghent Prison to keep people who were found guilty by the court. In 1776, the Walnut Street Prison in America began separating dangerous criminals from those who could change for the better. America also tried new ideas in prisons like those in Pennsylvania, Auburn, and Elmira, which became important examples of prison reform.

Since Nepal ratified the The International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, 1966 in 14 May 1991. As a state party, Nepal has international obligation to respect, protect and fulfill all human rights enunciated in the ICCPR. The **ICCPR** aims to ensure the protection of civil and political rights including:

- Freedom from discrimination
- Right to equality between men and women,
- Right to life,
- the states commit themselves to promote the right to self-determination and to respect that right.
- Recognizes the rights of peoples to freely own, trade and dispose of their natural wealth and resources.
- The freedom from prison due to debt is mentioned herein and Nepal has an international obligation to respect, protect and fulfill all the human rights are:-

“Each State Party shall keep under systematic review interrogation rules, instructions, methods and practices as well as arrangements for the custody and treatment of persons subjected to any form of arrest, detention or imprisonment in any territory under its jurisdiction, with a view to preventing any cases of torture”.

The **Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR)**,1948 being major human rights instruments has been ratified in Nepal since 1991 that pays right to life, liberty and the security of person and no one shall be subjected to torture or to cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment.

As the four Geneva Conventions offer protection to wounded and sick soldiers on land and at sea, prisoners of war and civilians. Nepal is a part to Geneva Convention, 1949 whereas the Government of Nepal didn't accede to additional IHL instruments, including two protocols of 1977 despite the conclusion of the comprehensive peace agreement and the formation of the new government.

1.1.1.2 In context of nepal

The history of prisons in Nepal began in 1971. The first prison in Nepal was "**Sardar Prison**" (currently the Prison Office Kathmandu - Jagannath Dewal). In 2019, the Prison Act 2079 was enacted to make provisions related to prisons, and the Prison Regulations 2020 were formulated and implemented by exercising the authority granted by Section 27 of the said Act. The Prison Act 2019 was repealed and the Prison Act 2079 has now been implemented, while the fifteenth amendment to the Prison Regulations 2020 has also been implemented.

In order to make prison management and administration work effective and robust, the Prison Management Department was established at the central level under the Ministry of Home Affairs from 1 Shrawan 2050. Out of the 77 districts of Nepal, there are 75 prison offices in 72 districts except 5 districts namely Dhanusha, Bara, Bhaktapur, East Nawalparasi and East Rukum. There are two places in Nepalgunj and Naubasta in Banke, two places in Ghorahi and Tulsipur in Dang district and two places in Jagannath Dewal (Sundhara) and Dillibazaar (Charkhal) in Kathmandu district. There is a provision that the concerned Chief District Officer has the general responsibility of prison management and administration at the local level. For the treatment of prisoners who have completed their sentences in prisons, the Central Prison Hospital in Kathmandu district and the Hospital for Psychosocially Disabled Prisoners in Lalitpur district are in operation. The construction of an open prison is underway in Ganapur, Banke. The Department of Prison Management has been providing support in the policy and administrative management of the prison office and prisoner management.

Overtime, there has been development of proper management system and quarterly progress report by the department is uploaded on their website on a regular basis with detailed information on prison, prisoners and detainees. Yet, some of the highlights are not timely uploaded to the public with limited informed on websites. The policy has been developed on the basis of various existing acts of Nepal including Constitution of Nepal, 2072, Prisons

Act 2079 and. Some of the major acts and regulations contributing in formulation of policy development for the Prison Management Department of Nepal are listed below:

- Constitution of Nepal 2072
- Prisons Act 2079
- Muluki Code (Civil Criminal) 2074
- Civil Service Act 2049
- Police act 2048 (Fifth amendment)
- The Prevention of Corruption act 2059
- Local administration Act 2028
- Prison regulation 2020 (15th Amendment)
- Civil Service Rules 2072 (12th amendment)
- The Criminal Offenses (Sentencing and Execution) Act, 2074

Crime comes also with custody, investigation, fine, bailment or imprisonment. The prisoners of Nepal are mainly kept in four major sentences;

- Life imprisonment
- Imprisonment,
- Imprisonment and fine, and defaulter.

While the people who are eligible to be released on bail are subjected to the orders in court, the weaker ones are equally voiced to raise up for legal aid. Without the weaker members of society having access to free legal aid, it is impossible to imagine universal access to justice. The prior aim of "Right to Justice" is to "ensure that opportunities for securing justice are not denied to any citizen by reason of economic or other disabilities," the article requires the state to advance justice based on equal opportunity and to offer free legal aid.

Currently, Nepal follows a mixed approach incorporating punitive and reformatory measures. The prison system includes;

Types of Prisons:

1. *Central Prisons*-For serious offenders (e.g. Sundhara Prison, Kathmandu).
2. *District Prisons*-Short-term detention centers.
3. *Open Prisons*-For low-risk prisoners with a focus on rehabilitation.
4. *Juvenile Reform Centers* ; For minors in conflict with the law.

‡ **Current Prison Conditions**

- Nepal's prison population has doubled in 13 years from 13,068 in 2011 to 29,484 in 2024, far exceeding the official capacity.
- Jagannath Dewal Prison holds 3,579 inmates (capacity: 2,200); Nakkhu holds 1,381 (capacity: 1,000); Dillibazaar has 633 inmates.
- Major crimes: rape (5,456), homicide (3,778), drug offenses (3,259); 1,514 are foreign nationals. Five districts (Dhanusha, Bara, Bhaktapur, East Nawalparasi, East Rukum) have no prisons.
- 439 inmates are above 65 years; 83 children live with incarcerated parents.
- 1,351 juveniles are held in 9 correctional homes, largest in Banke, Bhaktapur. and Morang.
- Health issues affect over 2,200 inmates in Jagannath Dewal.
- No regular human rights monitoring; deaths in custody (e.g., 18 in Morang) go uninvestigated.
- Current Infrastructure: Nepal operates 74 prisons across 72 districts, with Kathmandu and Dang each hosting two facilities.
- Living Conditions: Overcrowding has resulted in inadequate living conditions, including insufficient space, poor sanitation, and limited access to healthcare services.
- Informal Hierarchies: Within prisons, unofficial systems led by "chaukidars" and "naikes" have emerged, often leading to exploitation and internal violence.
- Rehabilitation Programs: Efforts are being made to implement rehabilitation programs focusing .

- on skill development and education to facilitate their integration of inmates into society. Alternative Sentencing: The Criminal Offences Sentencing and Execution Act envisions.
 - provisions for community service, open prisons, parole, and probation as alternatives to traditional imprisonment, aiming to reduce overcrowding and promote rehabilitation.
- Health Issues: Lack of medical facilities.
- Human Rights Concerns: Reports of abuse and insufficient legal aid.

Note:- The average cost of maintaining a prisoner in Nepal is approximately NPR 10,000 per month [Government Data] (www.kathmandupost.com).

1.1.2 Meaning of prison

The term “PRISON” means “a place properly arranged and equipped for reception of person whose legal processes are committed to it for safe custody while awaiting trial or for punishment.” The term “PRISON” means “a place for the confinement of people accused or convicted for a crime.”

In Nepalese context, '**Khor**' and '**Karagar**' is different.

According to the **Prison Act 2079**, Karagar is referred to a building; room or places in order to confine the prisoners (Kaidi) or detainees (Thunuwa) or acquired land of the buildings or room also.

Khor referred to the specified building, room or place and acquired land by such places in order to keep only for Thunuwa (the detainees).

M. J. Sethana has defined prison as 'A prison is a place for detention or under trials also they are the place when the offender can be lodged for his/her reformation.

1.1.3 Terminology used by different countries

The terminology used to describe or distinguish between prisons and other correctional facilities can vary between nations and jurisdictions.

Australia:-

In Australia, the words "gaol", "prison" and "prison" are commonly used. The spelling "gaol" was in official use in the past, and many historical gaols are now tourist attractions, such as the Maitland Gaol. Officially, the term "correctional centre" is used for almost all prisons in New South Wales and Queensland, while other states and territories use a variety of names. "Prison" is officially used for some facilities in South Australia, Victoria and Western Australia. Youth prisons in Australia are referred to as "youth correctional facilities" or "youth detention centres" among other names, depending on the jurisdiction.

Canada:-

In Canada, while the terms "prison" and "prison" are commonly used in speech, officially named facilities use "facility", "correctional centre", "penitentiary", or "institution".

A number of facilities retain their historical designation as a "prison".

New Zealand:-

In New Zealand, the terms "prison" and "prison" are commonly used, although the terms "correctional facility" and "prison" among others are in official usage.

Papua New Guinea:-

In Papua New Guinea, "prison" is officially used, although "prison" is widely understood and more common in usage.

United States of America:-

In American English, the terms prison and prison have separate uses, though this is not always adhered to in casual speech and the manner in which correctional facilities are officially described varies by state.

The term system means a set of connected things forming a complex whole in particular or a set of things working together as part of a mechanism or interconnecting network. So prison system also include whole area of confinement, its administration, mechanism covering all aspects of imprisonment. The term prison and prison are sometime used inter-changeably. Prison means any goal or penitentiary including the airing grounds and other grounds or buildings engaged for use of prison.”

1.1.4 Introduction to Birgunj Prison (Parsa District Prison)

Birgunj Prison, officially recognized as the Parsa District Prison, is one of Nepal’s most notable correctional institutions situated in the heart of Birgunj Sub-Metropolitan City, within Parsa District of Madhesh Province, Nepal. Located near the Indo-Nepal border and along Prison Road 5, the prison holds strategic importance due to its geographical proximity to India and its centrality within the Terai belt. The facility is under the jurisdiction of the **Department of Prison Management (DoPM)**, which functions under the Ministry of Home Affairs, Government of Nepal. It is also locally overseen by the **District Administration Office (DAO), Parsa.**

1.1.4.1 Historical Context and Establishment of Birgunj Prison

Birgunj Prison is one of the older penitentiary establishments in Nepal, dating back to the Rana regime — a period marked by centralized autocratic rule, when modern state institutions, including the judiciary and prison systems, were in their formative stages. The original infrastructure of the prison was constructed to house a limited number of inmates,

with a maximum capacity of around **500 detainees**, reflecting the relatively low crime rate and smaller population of the district at that time. However, over the decades, while the population and crime rates have grown exponentially, the prison infrastructure has remained largely stagnant, resulting in an acute mismatch between capacity and occupancy.

As a result, there is total capacity of prisoners with maximum 1000 along with increasing crime rate and increases population in this district.

1.2 Statement of Problem

This study examines the gap between legal provisions in Nepal's Prison Act and the actual conditions in Birgunj Prison, focusing on overcrowding, inadequate medical facilities, and poor living standards. It aims to assess compliance with legal standards, investigate the implementation of health and rehabilitation services, and identify the causes of systemic neglect and challenges in prison management.

1.3.Objective of the Birgunj Prison visit

I had kept the following as my objectives of Birgunj Prison visit ;

- a. To know the standard to be followed while entering into the Prison.
- b. To understand the different types of prison department authorities, their work identify the challenges faced in managing the faculty.
- c. To observe , evaluate the physical living conditions within the prison (Health facilities, overcrowding, etc.). & compare them with the standards outlined in the Prison Act and relevant national laws.
- d. To make valuable recommendation Or measures for improving the condition of the prison environment.

1.4 .Significance of the study

This study holds importance in highlighting the real conditions of inmates in Birgunj Prison and examining whether the prison environment complies with the standards set by the Prison Act 2079 B.S., the Constitution of Nepal 2072, and relevant international human rights instruments. By documenting the current state of infrastructure, healthcare, legal aid, and rehabilitation services, the research aims to:

- Provide valuable insights for policy-makers, human rights organizations, and law enforcement agencies to identify gaps and improve prison management.
- Support legal reforms and better implementation of prisoners' rights by presenting ground-level realities.
- Serve as a reference for future academic research, especially for law students, scholars, and social science researchers focused on criminal justice and correctional systems.
- Raise public awareness about prison conditions, thereby promoting transparency and accountability in the penal system.

1.5.Scope of the Study

The scope of this study is geographically limited to Birgunj Prison in Parsa District, Nepal. The research focuses on evaluating key aspects such as inmate living conditions, sanitation, medical facilities, access to legal aid, and administrative practices within the prison environment.

The legal scope of the study includes analysis of the Prison Act 2079 B.S., the Constitution of Nepal 2072, and relevant international legal instruments. The study is qualitative in nature, based on field observation, semi-structured interviews, and document review conducted during a short-term visit.

This study does not extend to other prisons or include in-depth statistical analysis. Instead, it offers a snapshot of current prison conditions in Birgunj Prison and serves as a foundation for broader comparative or longitudinal research in the future.

1.6 Limitation of study

- a. Limited access to certain prison areas due to security restrictions.
- b. Small number of inmates and staff interviewed; may not reflect overall conditions.
- c. Incomplete or unavailable official data (e.g., health records, budget reports).
- d. Possibility of biased responses due to observer presence and do not allow researcher with detained and prisoners .
- e. No professional psychiatric evaluation conducted during the visit.

CHAPTER:- 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1.By Republica Post

February 13, 2017 at 4:10 PM

BIRGUNJ, Feb 13: The Birgunj Prison, that has been housing inmates double the number of inmates than its authorized capacity, has been facing safety and security issues for sometimes now. The Prison built during the Rana reign and having capacity to house 500 inmates has limited space where a total of 1,227 of them including 210 Indian nationals have been put.

2.2 BY Kathmandu Post

The lack of a medical centre on the premises of Birgunj Prison has deprived the prisoners of immediate medical care when needed.

The prison currently holds more than 1,200 prisoners, according to the data of the prison administration. Cases of minor health issues among the patients are reported daily but since

there is no health centre on the prison premises, the patients are taken to Narayani Hospital for treatment. However, if a patient is in need of immediate care, delay in taking him to the hospital often leads to his worsening health condition and in some cases even death.

"In July 2018, 74-year-old inmate Dipan Shah fell ill. Shah, a chronic patient with high blood pressure and asthma, died on his way to a hospital," said Ashok Kumar Baidya, former president of Birgunj Chamber of Commerce and Industries.

2.3 Inmates in Birgunj prison subjected to torture, extortion

By Ritesh Tripathi

April 10, 2019 at 4:00 AM

BIRGUNJ, April 10: Some former inmates of the Birgunj Prison have made a shocking revelation about how the torture and violence by guards inside the prison compelled one of their friends to attempt suicide.

This is an incident of April 1. The inmate is from Dharan and he had injured his hand after falling unconscious inside the prison," said Police Inspector of Parsa, Rewati Dhakal, adding, "We have found that he needs some kind of psychological counseling but we have no idea whether it was an attempt to suicide.

CHAPTER:- 3

Methodology

This research is qualitative, descriptive, and exploratory in nature, conducted through a combination of both primary and secondary approaches. The methodology of this project is based on the review of secondary data and analysis of primary data collected from the

interview, field observation, and legal analysis. The methodology was designed to assess the prison conditions of Birgunj Prison in light of the provisions of the Prison Act, 2079 B.S., and relevant human rights standards.

3.1 Data collection method

A. Primary Method

Our site visit itself was a major method in which we collected valuable facts in the following way.

- **Field Observation:** Direct observation of prison conditions, including living detained person , school premises ,different department section etc.
- **Interviews:** Semi-structured or open Interviews with prison officials (prison superintendent, medical staff, guards) , Informal conversations with Experts to understand their experiences, problems, and legal awareness.

B. Secondary method :-

We were availed with more information collected from except eye witness in following ways :-

- locally available books , journals,
- History found in the internet sites i.e.websites
- Prison Act , 2079 &
- Newspaper, Article : Analysis of official records, legal documents, and previous reports for compliance with legal standards.

3.2 Data Interpretation & Analysis

- Finding are interpreted based on legal provisions, observed conditions, and participant feedback.

- Qualitative data is categorized under themes like health, legal aid, rehabilitation, and rights violations.

3.3 Legal Framework Analysis

- Reference to Prison Act 2079 B.S., Human Rights standards , and other related laws.
- Evaluation of the prison’s compliance with national and international legal standards.

CHAPTER:4

DATA ANALYSIS & DISCUSSION

4.1 Visitor Screening and Entry Procedures at Birgunj Jai

While specific visitation procedures for Birgunj Prison are not publicly detailed, general practices across Nepalese prisons, as outlined by the Department of Prison Management (DoPM), typically include:

- **Identity Verification:** Visitors are required to present valid government-issued identification, such as a citizenship certificate or passport.
- **Approval Check:** The prison staff verifies whether the visitor is on the inmate's approved visitation list.
- **Security Screening:** Visitors undergo security screenings, which may include metal detectors or pat-downs, to prevent contraband from entering the facility.
- **Item Restrictions:** Personal belongings are typically not allowed beyond the screening point.
- **Visitor Pass Issuance:** Upon successful verification and screening, a visitor pass is issued for entry.

Thus , all these standards has been recorded in Cameras for the future evidence during time of need.

4.2 Organizational set up of Prison

The Director General of Prisons, Birgunj is the Head of the Prison Department and is assisted by Addl.I.G.(P) and Deputy Inspector General of Prisons. A Prison Superintendent heads

each prisons and Deputy Superintendents, Assistant Superintendents, Head Warders and Warders assist him.

The custodial duties of the prisoners are performed by the Prison Staff where as the external security; Patrolling, search etc. are taken care by Birgunj Special Police, and Central Reserve Police Force.

A Battalion of Nepal Armed Police handles the escorting of the prisoners to the courts/hospitals etc.

A Resident Medical Officer heads the Medical Administration of all Prisons. Senior Medical Officers head the Medical administration of each prison assisted by Medical Officers and other Para-medical staff.

4.3 Compare Present condition of birgunj prison to past one with their legal provision

4.3.1 Prisoners Capacity & no of prisoners {Overcrowding}

By Republica

February 13, 2017 at 4:10 PM

BIRGUNJ, Feb 13: The Birgunj Prison, that has been housing inmates double the number of inmates than its authorized capacity, has been facing safety and security issues for sometimes now. The Prison built during the Rana reign and having capacity to house 500 inmates has limited space where a total of 1,227 of them including 210 Indian nationals have been put.

So As per increasing the crime rate and increases population **in parsa district ,** **the** capacity of prisoners has been extended with maximum 1000 . Although the number of prisoner has been kept more than beyond the capacity. The list of number of prisoners as shown in following table ...

Particular	Nepali		Foreign		Total
	Female	Male	Female	Male	
Prisoner	10	363	11	55	439
Detainer	36	706	8	137	887
Dependent Children	2	0	0	1	3
Total	48	1069	19	193	1329

Working Hours to meet with Prisoners

Visitors	Time
Relatives & Friends	11 :00 Am – 4 :00 Pm
Advocate / Counsels & Embassy officials	11:00 AM – 4:00 Pm

4.3.2Health Facilities

Ktm Post report ,2018

The lack of a medical centre on the premises of Birgunj Prison has deprived the prisoners of immediate medical care when needed. The prison currently holds more than 1,200 prisoners, according to the data of the prison administration. Cases of minor health issues among the patients are reported daily but since there is no health centre on the prison premises, the patients are taken to Narayani Hospital for treatment. However, if a patient is in need of immediate care, delay in taking him to the hospital often leads to his worsening health

condition and in some cases even death. "In July 2018, 74-year-old inmate Dipan Shah fell ill. Shah, a chronic patient with high blood pressure and asthma, died on his way to a hospital," said Ashok Kumar Baidya, former president of Birgunj Chamber of Commerce and Industries.

Inmates in Birgunj prison subjected to torture, extortion

By Ritesh Tripathi April 10, 2019 at 4:00 AM BIRGUNJ, April 10: Some former inmates of the Birgunj Prison have made a shocking revelation about how the torture and violence by guards inside the prison compelled one of their friends to attempt suicide. "This is an incident of April 1. The inmate is from Dharan and he had injured his hand after falling unconscious inside the prison," said Police Inspector of Parsa, Rewati Dhakal, adding, "We have found that he needs some kind of psychological counseling but we have no idea whether it was an attempt to commit suicide." Reportedly, the guards and leaders of the inmates rule the prison that accommodates more than 1,200 occupants. As per those who are out of prison after serving their prison term, many occupants have reached a stage where they have suicidal thoughts due to the torture they face. Those who dare to raise their voice against the suppression and extortion are transferred to another prison. When the discussions were did with DSP Suwarn Pokhrel then He told that I am new since in this prison so, I was not aware of this information.

But Currently no any kind Of anything happens whatever You asked.

Legal Provision

Arrangement of hospital or health post: (1) In each prison with more than 500 prisoners, one hospital with the prescribed number of beds and one health post in each prison with less than 500 prisoners shall be arranged.

(2) Unless a hospital or health post is arranged according to sub-section (1), the prison administrator shall coordinate with the government hospital or health

post near the place where the prison office is located and make arrangements for the health examination and treatment of the prisoners in the prison.

But, currently the number of prisoner is more than capacity 1000 i.e 1329 although there is one Health Assistant (HA) who managing health posts, are trained to diagnose and treat common illnesses, administer medications, and provide primary health service to thr health issues prisoner. if a patient in need of immediate care and have incurable illness then the patients are taken to Narayani Hospital for treatment. However if more serious then , the patients are taken to Hospitals in Valley KTM.

4.3.3 Education

Education facilities were providing for those who want to study from prison for both prisoners and their childrens .

✚ For Prisoners children

School in Prison

Name of School ;- Lotus Flower School

Classes: 3

Kinder garden: 1

One Principle

No of teacher:- 3

No of Student :- 60

‡ CLASS STRUCTURE

- Nursery to three
- There are 4 class-rooms inside the prison of Parsa District.

‡ FACILITIES AND FEES

- Private school (english medium studies)
- Admission fee per person Rs.100
- Monthly fee As Rs.200 per student
- One time deposite 500 per student

A school, amid Birgunj, in a prison building. Here, children whose parents are imprisoned can go to school. Besides primary education, the children are provided with safety and a daily warm meal.

The school comprises three classes and one preschool group. In total, there are 60 children, who attend school every day. Every day starts with a communal prayer and some gymnastic exercises. At the end of the school day, a communal prayer of thanks will be recited. Afterwards, most of the children go home, to their parent, aunt or uncle.

For some children, their way home leads them to prison. If both mother and father are imprisoned and the child is still young enough, he or she will live with the parents in prison. There, they must experience the horrific everyday life in prison. Our school enables them to escape from it at least for a couple of hours a day and allows them to be a child.

International Provision (Education for All)

Education is the basic building block of every society. It is the single best investment countries can make to build prosperous, healthy and equitable societies. Article 26 of the 1948 Universal

Declaration of Human Rights states that “Everyone has the right to education.”

- Ensuring Inclusive,
- Equitable and
- Quality Education and the Promotion of Lifelong Learning Opportunities for All,

Constitutional Provision

Art 31, Right relating to education: (1) Every citizen shall have the right of access to basic education.

(2) Every citizen shall have the right to get compulsory and free education up to the basic level and free education up to the secondary level from the State.

Art 39, Rights of the child: Sub Art (2) Every child shall have the right to education, health, maintenance, proper care, sports, entertainment and overall personality development from the families and the State.

Legal Provision

Sec 24 of Prison Act 2079 provides Education should be arranged for Prisoners :

- (1) Prison Administrator for education of prisoners Necessary arrangements should be made.
- (2) The prison administrator shall make necessary arrangements for basic education, secondary education, open education, technical and vocational education or distance education in case of more than the specified number of inmates.
- (3) The Prison Administrator shall make necessary arrangements for alternative education, nonformal education or training of a similar nature to illiterate prisoners.

- (4) The prison administrator may appoint a teacher from among the inmates in the prison for the teaching as per sub-section (3).
- (5) The teachers designated in accordance with sub-section (4) shall be given the remuneration and facilities as determined for the relevant level.
- (6) The prison administrator shall make arrangements for the prisoner who is required to take the higher education examination to participate in such examination.
- (7) The prison administrator may conduct programs such as moral education, yoga practice, and meditation for the purpose of improving the behavior of prisoners or promoting positive thoughts.
- (8) The Prison Administrator shall provide necessary study material to the prisoner.

Currently , the prisoners child would get well managed education in good environment according as per constitutional right along with all the basic facilities such as classroom ,library, sport activities football ,ECA activities and those who are prisoner got also facilities accordingly Prison Act 2079 in literal way.

As a result , 3 prisoners from Birgunj Prison took part in writing Class-12 NEB exams on 2081 B.S and 4 Prisoners took part in SEE exam on 2081 B.S . Even the examination is conducted and arrangements have been made inside the prison For those who want to continue their studies from prison .

4.3.4 Direct and Daily Expenses

The Head of prisoner shall make policies to allocate and distribute direct ,daily expenses and clothes as per their provision mentioned in prisoner regulation.

Sec 20 Prison Act 2079. Provisions regarding daily expenses and Clothing: (1) The Prison Administrator shall arrange daily ration for the prisoners.

(2) The prison administrator shall arrange for more nutritious food in addition to the ration prescribed in sub-section (1) for the chronically ill, mentally ill or seriously ill, pregnant and post-partum inmates.

(3) The prison administrator shall arrange for the prisoners to dress according to the season.

As per the current condition , 700 grams of rice and 80 rupees per day are given for the daily expenses received by the prisoners & Rs 1700-1800 for clothes per year as per budget allocation for prisoner daily expenses and clothes.

4.3.5 Employment facilities inside Prison.

Inside the prison , The prisoners would also get platform to show their skill and can earn money which help to increase their living standard by engaging in different work .

Legal Provision

Sec 26 of Prison Act 2079 provides the provision related to employment for prisoners: (1) If a factory has been established in the prison premises after obtaining permission under prevailing law, prisoners who are willing to work in such a factory can be employed.

(2) According to sub-section (1), a prisoner shall be paid a wage as prescribed, not less than the minimum wage as determined by the Government of Nepal on the basis of contribution.

However, workers who work part-time should be paid wages as specified on the basis of contribution.

Thus Birgunj Prison places emphasis on skill development and providing inmates with opportunities for employment and productive engagement. The facility houses various industries and vocational training centres where inmates can learn and acquire new skills. These industries may include textile manufacturing, carpentry, agriculture, and handicrafts. By engaging in productive work, inmates gain valuable skills that can contribute to their rehabilitation and reintegration into society upon release accordingly their work they got reasonable remuneration.

4.3.6 Activities Performed by different department in Birgunj Prison

❖ **Amenities:**

Birgunj Prison strives to provide basic amenities to ensure the well-being of its inmates. These amenities include clean water supply, sanitation facilities, and hygienic living conditions. The prison also offers recreational facilities such as sports grounds, libraries, and access to educational materials, fostering personal development and promoting a sense of normalcy within the facility.

❖ **Food**

The prison recognizes the importance of nutritious meals in maintaining the physical and mental health of the inmates. Birgunj Prison provides balanced and wholesome meals to meet the dietary requirements of the inmates. Special dietary considerations, such as religious or medical needs, are taken into account, ensuring that all inmates receive appropriate and sufficient nutrition.

❖ **Reformation and Rehabilitation Programs:**

Puzhal Prison is committed to the reformation and rehabilitation of its inmates. The facility offers various programs and initiatives aimed at addressing the root causes of criminal behaviour and facilitating the reintegration of prisoners into society. These programs may include educational courses, vocational training, counselling sessions, and mental health support. By equipping inmates with essential skills, education, and emotional support, the prison strives to promote positive change and reduce recidivism rates.

CHAPTER: 5

FINDINGS

- ❖ It has been seen that special standard to be while enter in the prison .

- ❖ It seems over-crowding is a big issue for lack of proper attention towards the inmates as the prison can capacity of only 1000 prisoners but it is accommodating near about 1329 prisoners, which is more than the capacity of the prison But there is provision of separate Male Prison and Female prison.
- ❖ There is one Health Assistant (HA) who managing health posts, are trained to diagnose and treat common illnesses, administer medications, and provide primary health service to thr health issues prisoner. if a patient in need of immediate care and have incurable illness then the patients are taken to Narayani Hospital for treatment. However if more serious then , the patients have been taken to Hospitals in Valley KTM.
- ❖ The prisoners child would get well managed education in good environment according as per constitutional right along with all the basic facilities and those who are prisoner got also facilities accordingly Prison Act 2079 in literal way due to lack of execution of law.
- ❖ Although 3 prisoners from Birgunj Prison took part in writing Class-12 exams on 2081 B.S and 4 Prisoners took part in SEE exam on 2081 B.S . Even the examination is conducted and arrangements have been made inside the prison For those who want to continue their studies from prison .
- ❖ 700 grams of rice and 80 rupees per day are given for the daily expenses provided to the prisoners & Rs 1700-1800 for clothes per year as per budget allocation for prisoner daily expenses and clothes.
- ❖ it has been seen that basic amenities clean water supply, sanitation facilities, and hygienic living conditions. The prison also offers recreational facilities such as sports grounds, libraries, and access to educational materials, fostering personal development and promoting a sense of normalcy within the facility.
- ❖ I was told by the Deputy Superintendent of Prison that the under trial prisoners can wear normal and it is mandatory for the convicted prisoners to wear uniform which was of white colour.
- ❖ For reformation and rehabilitation programs such as educational courses, vocational training, counselling sessions, and mental health support. By equipping inmates with

essential skills, education, and emotional support, the prison strives to promote positive change and reduce recidivism rates.

- ❖ Prisoners have been given the basic rights as per mentioned in prevailing act and international act as well.
- ❖ It was found that there are many prisoners of rape, drug and Homicide cases.
- ❖ As part of the vocational training for the prisoners, there was a complaint that there was no proper market arrangement for the prisoners, although the training was conducted in the making of mudha, dhaka cap, sewing short pants, and making wooden materials.
- ❖ Recently, it was found that the number of prisoners related to coercion and drugs is increasing.
- ❖ It was found that female prisoners lacked sanitary pads and were unable to openly express their problems.
- ❖ It was found that there is an arrangement for the prisoners to make telephone calls, and it was also reported that the fee was fixed rupees per minute, but there was also a complaint that the arrangement was not literally implemented.
- ❖ It was found that the number of prisoners was more than the capacity and there were few meeting rooms, so the meeting time with the relatives was less and personal privacy could not be maintained.
- ❖ Although there is a post of health worker, it is found to be only one who provides primary health service only.
- ❖ It was found that there are facilities like sport for the entertainment of dependent children.
- ❖ It was found that there is a separate room for senior citizens.
- ❖ There is a general type of library for the prisoners.
- ❖ There is no discrimination has been in the name of caste, culture, religion, colour, sex etc

CHAPTER:6

CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATIONS

The visit to Birgunj jail gave us a better understanding of how the prison System works in Nepal. We saw that the jail is trying to improve the condition of prisoners through education and basic facilities. However, many challenges like overcrowding, Lackof mental health care, andlimited resources still exist. The management is doing its best, but more support is needed. Thisreport help us understand both the progress and the problems inside the jail system.

Regarding the prison of Birgunj , Parsa District under the Madhesh Province, the on-site monitoring of the district prisons from 13th Chaitra 2081 and the discussion and interaction with the officials were been working in the prison and employees of the respective districts. The following conclusions and suggestions have been presented focusing on policy and other issues.

6.1 Physical Structure

- ❖ Within the monitored prison building, it seems that there is a need to upgrade the existing building and build a new building so that there is enough space for sports, library, gymnasium and music room, room management to allow air and light to penetrate, as well as the number and capacity of prisoners.
- ❖ In order to implement the open prison concept provided in the law, it seems that the necessary budget should be allocated to search for a new location in accordance with international standards.
- ❖ There is no separate room for meetings with relatives and lawyers, it is seen that the privacy of prisoners and prisoners cannot be maintained, so it seems that arrangements should be made to maintain personal privacy for meetings in Birgunj Prison.

6.2 Direct and Daily Expenses

- ❖ It seems that the clothes and bedding provided to the prisoners should be distributed according to the appropriate quality according to the geographical conditions and climate.
- ❖ 700 grams of rice and 80 rupees per day for the daily expenses currently received by the prisoners are not enough according to the current market price.

6.3 Internal Management

- ❖ It seems that in order to arrange a sufficient budget for prison reform, prisoners and detainees who are over capacity should be transferred to prisons with fewer prisoners and detainees.
- ❖ According to the seriousness of the crimes committed by the prisoners, the prisoners should be kept separately in the prison and necessary arrangements should be made.
- ❖ Problems such as water leaking from the roof during the rainy season in the prisons , lack of toilets based on the number of inmates.

6.4 Healthcare

- ❖ It Seems that mental and physical health treatment services with skilled doctors should be provided based on the number of inmates and children in prisons and correctional homes to make the health examination system effective. Also, it seems that sanitary pads and other materials should be provided to women during menstruation.
- ❖ It seems that special arrangements should be made in prisons for differently abled, pregnant women, dependent children and senior citizens.

6.5 Security Management

- ❖ It seems that provision should be made for the periodic transfer of security personnel and employees, keeping in mind the financial and other relationships prohibited by law between the security personnel, employees and prisoners.
- ❖ When preparing the personal details of the prisoners and transferring them from one prison to another, it seems that the details should also be sent together.

REFERENCES;

- Prison Act, 2079 B.S. – Government of Nepal
- The Constitution of Nepal, 2072 B.S. (2015) – Nepal Law Commission.
- Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948) – United Nations.
- International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) – United Nations, 1966.
- Department of Prison Management, Annual Report – Ministry of Home Affairs, Government of Nepal <https://www.dopm.gov.np/en/>
- 6. Nepal Law Commission. (n.d.). Legal Provisions Related to Prison Management in Nepal.
- Department of Prison System <https://www.dopm.gov.np/en/>
- <https://hr.parliament.gov.np/uploads/attachments/d0qkyq2u70biwc2y.pdf>
- Kathmandu News ,The Republica & others news report.

APPENDICES

Visitsite :-Birgunj Prison

Prison Names along with prisoners Capacities in Nepal

Appendix H

Prison Capacity

S.no	Name of the prison	Capacity
1	Jhapa	300
2	Ilam	455
3	Panchthar	65
4	Taplejung	50
5	Morang	300
6	Bhojour	40
7	Dhankuta	40
8	Tehrathum	30
9	Sankhuwasabha	55
10	Sunsari	1500
11	Saptari	155
12	Siraha	150
13	Udayapur	40
14	Khotang	126
15	Solukhumbu	25
16	Okhaldhunga	30
17	Mahotari	200
18	Sarlahi	100
19	Sindhuli	50
20	Ramechapp	100
21	Dolakha	36
22	Parsa	1000
23	Chitwan	225
24	Rautahat	100
25	Makwanpur	335
26	Kathmandu	1500
27	Dillibazar	300
28	Lalitpur	250

S.no	Name of the prison	Capacity
29	Kavre	75
30	Nuwakot	80
31	Sindhupalchowk	150
32	Rasuwa	50
33	Dhading	55
34	Kaski	225
35	Tanahu	55
36	Syanja	50
37	Gorkha	50
38	Lamjung	35
39	Manag	6
40	Rupandehi	150
41	Nawalparasi	35
42	Kapilvastu	100
43	Palpa	275
44	Gulmi	25
45	Arghakhachi	25
46	Bagalung	50
47	Mayagdi	25
48	Mustang	25
49	Parwat	40
50	Tulasipur	100
51	Ghorahi	70
52	Salyan	35
53	Rolpa	50
54	Pyuthan	25
55	Rukum	35
56	Banke	150
57	Surkhet	50
58	Bardiya	150
59	Dailekha	25
60	Jajarkot	20

S.no	Name of the prison	Capacity
61	Jumla	10
62	Humla	20
63	Dolpa	20
64	Mugu	25
65	Kalikot	25
66	Bajhang	25
67	Bajura	25
68	Doti	25
69	Acham	120
70	Kailali	100
71	Kamchanpur	75
72	Baitadhi	25
73	Dadeldura	25
74	Darchula	65
	Total	10433

